

PERSPECTIVES ON CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT FOR CONTINUED TRAINING PROGRAMS FOR SCHOOL MANAGERS

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Abstract

The article addresses an issue in the field of professionalization of school management, which is among the priority themes in educational policies and research, at European and national level. The development of the curriculum of school manager training programs represents, in this context, one of the fundamental educational strategies, with a great impact on the quality of the training and professional development process and, ultimately, in the development and affirmation of desirable managerial skills.

The type of article is of a theoretical and fundamental nature, through a unitary approach of three dimensions:

a) analysis of the fundamental and correlative concepts of the professionalization process of school managers; b) systematization of reference frameworks regarding the areas of competence of the school manager, accompanied by the development of an own model, which includes the dimensions of professional training, as well as the capacities and skills necessary for the anticipated developments in the field;

c) defining perspectives and curricular development strategies, at the national level, that would facilitate the development of categories of managerial skills and constitute premises for research and innovations in educational management.

Keywords : professionalization of school management; school manager training curriculum;

reference frameworks regarding the categories of school manager competencies; curricular development of school manager training programs.

1. Conceptual approaches

The aim of professionalizing school management represents a strategic target of educational policies and strategies, with an impact on significant developments in conceptual, methodological and curricular terms. The perspectives that configure the conceptual and curricular frameworks of the issue are: the process of professionalizing school management; the curricular development of school manager training programs; the system of general competencies desirable for school managers.

The professionalization of school management represents, first and foremost and in a generic sense, a paradigm outlined at the intersection of several fundamental areas or issues: initial and continuous training in the

educational system; management of educational programs and projects; curriculum management; quality management in education. *The process of professionalization of managers* represents the set of training programs, projects and curricular strategies, which operationalize the conceptual and curricular reference models in the training and professional development of school managers, in the sense of developing the desirable competence profile, outlined at the level of educational policy and the personal professional project, as well as in the spirit of the culture of quality in initial and continuous training.

In Romania, school managers are recruited from among teachers, thus following a process of professionalization in the teaching career and having certified specialization skills and psychopedagogical skills, including those of educational process management. School manager training programs are organized in the two stages specific to the career in the educational system, namely: a) in initial training, through master's programs in educational management, without being mandatory, but with increased impact in the formation of managerial skills, due to the consistency and coherence of training in the university environment; b) in continuous training, through accredited programs and courses or through different forms and modalities in non-formal contexts and managerial self-training.

By virtue of the desire for professionalization and successful management, the professional school manager is a graduate of an initial training program in educational management, the specialized training being completed or expanded by following continuing education programs.

The curricular development of these types of training programs brings together the processes of analysis, resizing or expansion, at the level of structural elements (purposes, contents, training strategies), of procedural elements or of curricular products (curriculums, curricular programs, learning

supports), with implications for increasing the relevance, consistency and operability of the framework curriculum or the curriculum of thematic disciplines/modules.

The system of general competencies desirable for school managers is structured on categories of specific competencies from several subdomains of school management and relative to all dimensions of the professional profile in school management, whose balanced articulation and affirmation ensures the achievement of specific tasks and institutional and personal projects . The professional school manager has a competency profile developed by integrating all categories of desirable competencies, affirmed through high performance and by crystallization of organizational values desirable for postmodernism in education, as well as the ability to generate innovations in institutional development, all of which have a direct impact on the personal development of students.

2. Curricular milestones and strategies in the continuing education of school managers

If the master's programs in Educational Management have a scientifically based curriculum and curricular benchmarks that guide the training process in a comprehensive and professional manner, in terms of continuing education, resizing and curricular developments are necessary, in the perspective of a management training strategy.

The fundamental benchmark, which legitimizes and guides the training processes, is the defined and assumed competence profile. The specialized literature indicates several categories of competences, the combined affirmation of which facilitates the achievement of managerial objectives. Thus, several perspectives of approach are revealed in the definition and analysis of the school manager's competences:

- defining and analyzing the capacities, skills and attitudes necessary for specific managerial activities in correlation with the affirmation of the school manager's personality, so that the instrumental-managerial and leadership dimensions are optimally correlated (Joița, 1995, p.23-30, Bush, 2021, p. 215-230, Orțan , 2021, p 97-111);

- focusing institutional management mainly on optimizing classroom management and on students' personal development processes (Stan, Manea, 2013, p. 10-16);

- focusing on institutional project management, as a tool for school management policy and educational leadership, as well as on affirming the school's identity and institutional capacity in the context of educational marketing (Albulescu, Glava , Manea, Stan, 2025, Bunăiașu , 2012, p. 33 - 37);

- affirming the elements of professional identity, which crystallize transversal skills and facilitate managerial creativity (Strungă, 2014, p.149-170).

A reference framework on the general competence areas of the school manager, which regulates continuing education programs, it can be structured as follows (adapted from Bunăiașu , 2012, p. 33-37):

- *Cognitive skills*, which facilitate the acquisition of a scientific and operationalizable managerial culture.

- *Methodological skills* , affirmed through the capacities of strategic design and planning, organization, coordination of implementation, monitoring, evaluation and review of institutional and educational projects and programs.

- *Competencies in the field of human resources management and evaluation* , distributed on several levels, of an instrumental-managerial

nature (recruitment and selection, evaluation and guidance of teaching staff), as well as of a transversal nature (communication and relationships, implicative management): implicative management , crisis management, communication management.

- *Skills in using new educational technologies* and artificial intelligence, in creating virtual communities in school management .

- *Entrepreneurial skills and educational marketing*, identifying and managing additional resources and providing educational services.

- *Economic and financial skills* , efficient management and procurement of the resources necessary to develop the material base and support projects.

- *Research skills* in the field of educational management and innovation of managerial processes.

- *Transversal competencies, of an axiological nature* , focused on the development of organizational culture, on the promotion of inclusion, interculturality, and social education objectives;

- *Self-management skills for professional development* , through the development, management implementation and self-monitoring of personal projects, with impact on personal and institutional development.

A preliminary analysis, based on the correlation between the proposed reference framework of desirable managerial competencies and the continuing training programs offered by training providers, reveals:

a. the approach of only some categories of general skills, on the one hand, as well as the inconsistency of the curricular strategies used, not yet adapted to the constructivist paradigm, to management based on new educational technologies and virtual communities;

b. the imbalance in the curriculum of training programs, between the instrumental-managerial dimension, predominantly addressed, and the axiological-transversal one; even if, lately, an attempt has been made to re-dimension the curriculum through programs that address inclusive management, educational leadership, management of educational crisis situations, managerial communication or project management, large-scale curricular expansions are needed to compensate for the insufficiently addressed dimensions of training.

Based on these findings, we propose three directions for curricular development of continuing education programs for school managers, which include curricular strategies focused on the integral development of the managerial competence profile:

1. The introduction of disciplines or modules that address the axiological-transversal competences, as well as from areas that target creativity and managerial innovation at the instrumental-managerial level.
2. Adopting innovative curricular strategies, adapted to postmodern school management: constructivist strategies applied in educational management; new educational technologies and strategies for capitalizing on artificial intelligence; collaborative projects in virtual environments; strategies specific to educational leadership models; methodologies and tools for developing individual and group creativity.
3. Applying, appropriately and creatively, curriculum management strategies in the analysis of learning needs training, in design, organization, implementation, evaluation and review, correlated with qualitative research methodology in institutional management and with quality management strategies of training programs.

3. Conclusions

The unitary approach to the categories of managerial skills and the specified curricular development directions represent strategic options in the training policy of school managers and in the professionalization of the school manager function. In the analyzed perspective, the curriculum of the training programs targets several hypostases of the school manager, with an impact on his integral development: specialist manager, reflective manager, leader, research manager, counselor manager, project manager, pro-active manager.

In this context, educational research aims at the relationships between the curricular development of school manager training programs and the affirmation of managerial skills in strategic and operational management, with an impact on increasing school performance and institutional development. Examples of curricular development issues that can be the subject of research, with a view to validation as disciplines or modules of continuing education programs, are: Developing the school's organizational culture; Project management in the context of the postmodern school; School management centered on virtual communities in partnership contexts; Educational marketing; Professional identity and teaching career management; Self-management of the school manager's professional development.

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